

ISic3375

I.Sicily inscription 3375

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Heraea

Place of origin (modern)

Ragusa

Provenance

From tomb 15 of the archaic necropolis in contrada Cuciniello/Cucinello, excavated by Orsi in 1898, vicinity of Ragusa station

Coordinates

36.915712, 14.729270

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 19048

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 41.5 cm

Width 45 cm

Depth 9 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-4: 40-95 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. οἴμ[ου]
2. Ἐπ' Ἀλδ[---]
3. ο το Σαν[ι]
4. ρο

Apparatus

Text after Arena

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645603

PHI 330048

Bibliography

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014